
Analysis Framework for Mapping Inclusive Education Policies

EUROPEAN AGENCY
for Special Needs and Inclusive Education

ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK FOR MAPPING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION POLICIES

European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education

The European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (the Agency) is an independent and self-governing organisation. The Agency is co-funded by the ministries of education in its member countries and by the European Commission via an operating grant within the European Union (EU) Erasmus+ education programme (2014–2020).

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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ISBN: 978-87-7110-862-0 (Electronic)

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INTRODUCTION

This document presents an analysis framework that has been developed to map inclusive education policies. Specifically, it has been developed to systematically record available documentary evidence on country policies for inclusive education in a highly structured way. The analysis framework has been developed as a result of the different aspects of policy analysis work by the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education. It has notably been used in some of the projects financed by the European Commission Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP). It has the potential to be further developed and used in other policy analysis work.

The material presented here is [open-source](#). Country stakeholders can adapt and develop it for use in specific national-, regional- or local-level situations, providing a reference to the original source is given.

Background

The European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (the Agency) is an independent organisation that acts as a platform for collaboration for the ministries of education in its 31 member countries. Agency work focuses on improving the achievement of all learners, at all levels of the education system. This enhances learners' life chances and opportunities for active participation in society.

The [Agency position paper](#) sets out the Agency member countries' shared vision for inclusive education. It states that: 'all learners of any age' should be 'provided with meaningful, high-quality educational opportunities in their local community, alongside their friends and peers' (European Agency, 2015, p. 1). This vision is the focal point of all Agency work.

The Agency aims to help member countries to improve their educational policy and practice by combining the perspectives of policy, practice and research to provide evidence-based information and guidance on implementing inclusive education.

In recent years, in addition to thematic project work, the Agency has undertaken activities that support countries to systematically reflect upon their policies for inclusive education. These include:

- [Country Policy Review and Analysis](#) (CPRA) activities.¹
- The provision of technical support to the ministries of education in two Agency member countries under the auspices of the European Commission [Structural Reform Support Programme](#). Both activities are fully funded by the Commission. They concern legislative educational changes regarding inclusive education, in line with the priorities at European and international levels.
- Audits of the systems for inclusive education in two other member countries.

¹ The CPRA work has been conducted with 21 countries. It provides countries with a reflection on their current policy frameworks for inclusive education.

All of these activities involve different forms of information analysis regarding policy for inclusive education that support reflection and discussion in the countries concerned.

Development of the analysis framework

The analysis framework is a tool for the detailed mapping of international-, European- and national-level information on country systems for inclusive education. This involves examining a range of documents relating to legislation and policy.

The framework draws on methods and content that have been validated through activities that the Agency has conducted with its 31 member countries.

Methodology

The development process for the mapping framework is based on the [CPRA methodology](#) (European Agency, 2018) and working procedures.

The framework is based on a grid designed to record information from documentary evidence regarding inclusive education. The grid outlines the main components of inclusive education systems identified in the Agency position paper and approved by Agency member country representatives (who are nominated by their respective ministries of education). The main components are described below.

Legislation and policy for inclusive education systems

Legislation and policy for inclusive education systems need to be underpinned by a fundamental commitment to ensuring every learner's right to inclusive education. Legislation and policy must be guided by an agreed vision and must emphasise the shared responsibility of all educators, leaders and decision-makers to enact the vision.

Legislation and policy are covered separately in [Section 1](#) of the mapping framework grid:

1.1 [Legislation](#)

1.2 [Policy](#).

Operational structures and processes

Operational structures and processes within inclusive education systems are guided by the principles of equity, effectiveness and efficiency. These structures and processes aim to raise the achievement of all system stakeholders.

Six operational structures and processes have been identified. [Section 2](#) of the mapping framework presents them. These align with the elements identified in the 'ecosystem model of support for inclusive education'. The ecosystem model was developed within the [Inclusive Early Childhood Education](#) project (European Agency, 2017a), built on in the [Raising the Achievement of All Learners in Inclusive Education](#) project (European Agency, 2017b) and applied within the [audit of Iceland's inclusive education system](#) (European Agency, 2017c). The elements are:

2.1 [System capacity-building](#)

2.2 [Governance and funding](#)

- 2.3 [Monitoring, quality assurance and accountability](#)
- 2.4 [Initial and continuing professional development opportunities](#)
- 2.5 [Learning and teaching environments](#)
- 2.6 [Continua of support](#).

These structures and processes apply across all national education systems, from pre-primary through to the end of upper-secondary education. The framework can therefore be used to examine all of these levels – or any one of them individually.

The grid

The final grid contains eight sub-sections, as outlined above.

In line with the Agency's CPRA methodology, each sub-section includes a number of relevant recommendations. These recommendations are taken from Agency projects and activities conducted between 2010 and 2017.²

All recommendations have been approved by Agency member countries – either collectively by all representatives, by smaller working groups or, in the case of the two audit reports, by individual countries' ministries of education.

The recommendations are not in priority order but, as far as possible, overarching recommendations are identified first, with more specific points following on.

In order to direct documentary analysis work, the recommendations have been expressed as **mapping questions**.

Documentary analysis

This analysis should be based on a wide range of documents generated by and relating to each country's educational legislation and policies. The analysis aims to find evidence that a recommendation has been taken into account.

This evidence may be taken from the country's legislation, policy or supporting documentation that shows that the following criteria have been met:

- **Legislation** exists.
- **Policy** statements have been made.
- Quality assurance **measures, frameworks** and/or **mechanisms** exist.
- **Requirements** are made of professionals and schools.
- **Tools** or **guidance** documents are available.
- **Standards** are in place.

² The projects and activities used as the basis for the mapping framework grid are: [Early Childhood Intervention](#) and [Inclusive Early Childhood Education; Mapping the Implementation of Policy for Inclusive Education; Organisation of Provision; Teacher Education for Inclusion](#) and [Empowering Teachers; Assessment in Inclusive Settings; ICT for Inclusion](#) and [i-access](#); Key Principles for [Policy](#) and [Practice](#); [Vocational Education and Training; Raising Achievement for All Learners](#) and [Raising the Achievement of All Learners in Inclusive Education; Financing of Inclusive Education; Early School Leaving; Luxembourg Recommendations](#); Country Audit reports from [Malta](#) and [Iceland](#); [CPRA work](#).

- **Data** is available.

Documents used in the analysis may include national-level legislation, policy, guidance and/or supporting documents, national analysis reports and international and European-level commentaries on country legislation and policy.

Initially, it may be helpful to scan the approved documents using an agreed list of search terms. If the scan highlights relevant information, a short quote or extract from the document should be noted in the grid as evidence. Each quote/extract should be referenced with the document name, page number and a weblink (if available). All documents used should be listed in a final bibliography.

If the initial scan does not identify relevant information for further consideration, a more detailed scan of the content can be conducted. If no results are highlighted, the document can be excluded from further analysis.

Two kinds of evidence or **findings** can be identified:

- **General findings** that apply across the education system
- **Specific findings** that only apply to a specific system sector/level or thematic area.

These sector-/level-specific findings should be clearly differentiated in the grid.

A profile of strengths and challenges

Findings indicate **strengths** within the legislative and policy framework. They show that the recommendations have been addressed – wholly or in part – and that the [criteria](#) in one or more of the seven bullet points listed above have been met.

The framework can also highlight **challenges** in relation to specific recommendations where criteria have not been met. This may indicate possible areas for system development and future work.

In effect, the mapping provides a **system profile** that shows strengths and areas for development in legislation, policy and operational structures and processes for the country's inclusive education system.

The following pages present the mapping framework grid.

SECTION 1: LEGISLATION AND POLICY FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SYSTEMS

1.1 Legislation

This sub-section examines whether country legislation is underpinned by a fundamental commitment to ensuring every learner's right to inclusive and equitable educational opportunities.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include:

- legislation and legislative regulations for the special needs and/or inclusive education system;
- national, European and international documents commenting on the country's legislation for education generally and special needs/inclusive education specifically;
- other supporting documentation, e.g. Ombudsman's reports.

Table 1. Mapping questions for legislation

1.1.1 Is the concept of inclusion in education clearly defined in legislation as an agenda that increases quality and equity for all learners?
1.1.2 Is legislation underpinned by a fundamental commitment to ensuring every learner's right to inclusive and equitable educational opportunities and consistent with the principles of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) ?
1.1.3 Is legislation underpinned by a fundamental commitment to ensuring every learner's right to inclusive and equitable educational opportunities and consistent with the principles of all relevant European equality, anti-discrimination and disability rights directives ?
1.1.4 Does legislation aim to address the underachievement of all vulnerable groups , including children with disabilities?
1.1.5 Is legislation for inclusive education at all system levels cross-sectoral and cross-ministerial ?
1.1.6 Does legislation have the goal of ensuring educational services that enhance developments and processes working towards equity in inclusive education?
1.1.7 Is the requirement to take learners' views into account in all educational processes outlined in legislation?

1.1.8 Is the **requirement to take families' views into account** in all educational processes outlined in legislation?

1.1.9 Does legislation ensure **the same quality of service** irrespective of differences in geographical location? (*Such as isolated or rural areas*).

1.2 Policy

This sub-section examines whether country policy provides a clear vision for and conceptualisation of inclusive education as an approach for improving all learners' educational opportunities. It also explores whether the shared responsibility of all educators, leaders and decision-makers in enacting the vision is emphasised.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include:

- all relevant policy documents and statements (codes of practice; details of national targets and goals for education);
- policy implementation guidelines;
- regulations, etc., for the general education system;
- all relevant policy documents for the special needs and/or inclusive education system;
- national, European and international documents commenting on the country's policy framework for education generally and special needs/inclusive education specifically;
- other supporting documentation, e.g. Ombudsman's reports.

Table 2. Mapping questions for policy

1.2.1 Is policy guided by a clear vision that inclusive education increases quality and equity for all learners?
1.2.2 Does policy support the implementation of every learner's right to inclusive and equitable educational opportunities and is it consistent with the principles of the UNCRC and the UNCRPD ?
1.2.3 Does policy support the implementation of every learner's right to inclusive and equitable educational opportunities and is it consistent with all relevant European equality, anti-discrimination and disability rights directives ?
1.2.4 Does policy aim to widen access to education and promote full participation and opportunities for all learners vulnerable to exclusion to realise their potential?
1.2.5 Is there a long-term, multi-level policy framework for implementing quality inclusive education at national, regional and/or organisational levels?
1.2.6 Does policy have the goal of increasing enrolment rates and participation in high-quality inclusive early childhood education and care?
1.2.7 Does policy ensure that pre-school places are offered to children coming from early childhood education services/provision?

1.2.8 Does policy outline how cost-free services/provision across all system levels are provided for learners and their families as early as possible and as quickly as possible , following identification of need?
1.2.9 Does policy outline the support available for families to enable them to recognise and understand their child's needs?
1.2.10 Does policy state that, in risk situations , the child's rights should come first?
1.2.11 Does policy have the goal of ensuring the full involvement of families in all educational processes?
1.2.12 Does policy clearly respect the rights and the needs of children and their families , taking their views and opinions into account in all educational processes?
1.2.13 Are policy goals and objectives for inclusive education clearly integrated in all areas of general education policy ?
1.2.14 Is policy for inclusive education cross-sectoral ?
1.2.15 Are policies based upon universal design and all-inclusive principles ?
1.2.16 Does policy outline procedures to ensure the efficient co-ordination of services with clearly defined roles and responsibilities?
1.2.17 Does policy describe an effective framework of support for schools to implement inclusive education across all system levels?
1.2.18 Do local (regional/municipality) level policies aim to reduce system inequities and fragmentation across regions?
1.2.19 Do local (regional/municipality) level policies aim to promote more equitable and effective provision for all learners?

SECTION 2: OPERATIONAL STRUCTURES AND PROCESSES

This section examines whether the overall inclusive education system is guided by the principles of equity, effectiveness, efficiency and raising the achievements of all system stakeholders.

The possible documents to be analysed in this section include:

- quality assurance frameworks;
- Ombudsman’s reports;
- guidance for schools;
- requirements for professionals;
- curriculum tools or guidance documents;
- standards for practice and services;
- different forms of system data (qualitative/quantitative; review and evaluation, etc.).

2.1 System capacity-building

This sub-section examines whether there are processes for developing and strengthening professionals’ attitudes, skills and abilities. It also considers the support and resources that educational organisations and communities require to develop the necessary working procedures for inclusive education.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include:

- descriptions of system organisation (regional and/or municipality structures for education);
- guidance on respective roles and responsibilities;
- cross-sectoral co-operation;
- Ombudsman’s reports.

Table 3. Mapping questions for system capacity-building

2.1.1 Are there clearly defined <i>strategies</i> to increase the capacity of all schools to meet a greater diversity of needs and support learners within their local communities?
2.1.2 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to facilitate national dialogue to develop a shared understanding of inclusive education ?

2.1.3 Is there a <i>strategy</i> to enable all stakeholders to develop a shared understanding of inclusive education as an approach that ensures high-quality learning opportunities for all?
2.1.4 Is there clear <i>guidance</i> on what the enactment of learners' rights looks like in practice across all system levels?
2.1.5 Is there clear <i>guidance</i> on what inclusive education looks like in practice across all system levels?
2.1.6 Is there a clear <i>strategy</i> to build the capacity of all support systems at all levels?
2.1.7 Is there clear <i>guidance</i> on inclusive learning environments that addresses age, phase and geographical inequities in access to provision and resources, guaranteeing a minimum level of support for all learners?
2.1.8 Are there <i>guidelines</i> that support schools to work as professional learning communities ?
2.1.9 Are there <i>guidelines</i> that support schools to improve school community co-operation by involving parents and a wide range of partners in formal and informal networks?
2.1.10 Are there clear <i>guidelines</i> on how methods of assessment, school evaluation, inspections and other accountability measures contribute to school improvement processes ?
2.1.11 Are there <i>strategies</i> to support schools to build strong leadership teams and distribute tasks among all school stakeholders?
2.1.12 Are there clear <i>incentives</i> for schools to accept and enrol all learners from their local community?
2.1.13 Are there clearly defined <i>strategies</i> for developing the role of specialist provision (separate schools, classes and units) as a resource to increase the capability of mainstream schools?
2.1.14 Are there clear <i>mechanisms</i> to support improvement in schools with lower educational outcomes ?
2.1.15 Are there clear <i>mechanisms</i> to address underachievement and drop-out of learners from vulnerable groups, including learners with disabilities?

2.2 Governance and funding

This sub-section examines the structures and processes that are designed to ensure accountability, transparency and responsiveness of the system for inclusive education. It also examines how the funding and resourcing system supports inclusive education.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include:

- general education expenditure figures;
- inclusive education expenditure figures;
- descriptions of additional support decision-making procedures, including information on school governance and dispute mediation procedures;
- role/input from other services in decision-making.

Table 4. Mapping questions for governance and funding

2.2.1 Is there a governance <i>mechanism</i> that supports effective implementation of inclusive education at all system levels ?
2.2.2 Are there clearly defined <i>strategies</i> for supporting effective professional collaboration , inter-agency and multi-disciplinary working across all system levels ?
2.2.3 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that governance aims, processes and structures are clearly communicated to system stakeholders?
2.2.4 Is there clear <i>guidance</i> outlining how delegated responsibilities will be implemented and supported?
2.2.5 Is there clear <i>guidance</i> providing clarification on the degrees of freedom and flexibility available for municipalities and schools?
2.2.6 Are all governance <i>strategies</i> guided by the goal of improving the cost-effectiveness of the education system, combining efficiency, effectiveness, equity and inclusion?
2.2.7 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> for systematic data collection on expenditure that informs cost-effectiveness issues?
2.2.8 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that inclusive education policies are linked to long-term financial support for flexible resourcing frameworks ?
2.2.9 Are there financial <i>incentives</i> to encourage all schools to develop policies and action plans for inclusive education?
2.2.10 Are there clear <i>strategies</i> to support schools to use general funding base allocations more flexibly ?

2.2.11 Are there clear *mechanisms* to implement a shift in funding systems **away from mainly input funding approaches, towards throughput funding approaches**?³

2.2.12 Are there clear *strategies* to **review current funding approaches** to identify any potential imbalance in funding allocations across regions, municipalities, school phases, services, schools, groups or individual learners?

2.2.13 Are there *strategies* to ensure **long-term funding commitments to support collaborative initiatives** between various school-based resource centres and research teams?

2.2.14 Are there *mechanisms* to ensure that the **outcomes of investments** made in inclusive systems are **monitored and clearly communicated** to other system stakeholders?

³ An input-based funding model relates funds directly to an individual learner's official decision of special educational needs. A throughput model connects the provision of funds and resources to the school's ability to meet the diverse range of educational needs all learners may have.

2.3 Monitoring, quality assurance and accountability

This sub-section examines the policies, procedures and practices designed to achieve, maintain and enhance quality in inclusive education. It also examines how educational organisations account for their activities, accept responsibility for them and share information on their results openly and transparently.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include descriptions of school accountability, inspection and school quality assurance procedures relating to:

- curriculum;
- teaching;
- assessment;
- school organisation;
- leadership;
- financing;
- outcomes and results;
- school internal review procedures;
- requirements for school development planning;
- school review pilot project outcomes;
- consideration of regional differences.

Table 5. Mapping questions for monitoring, quality assurance and accountability

2.3.1 Is there a comprehensive cross-sectoral/cross-ministerial <i>policy framework</i> for improving the quality of all education professionals' work ?
2.3.2 Is there a comprehensive accountability <i>framework</i> for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of national-level inclusive education policy?
2.3.3 Do all policy <i>measures and guidelines</i> clearly define common quality standards for services and provision across health, education and social services?
2.3.4 Is there a <i>framework</i> of quality assurance processes and procedures that applies to all schools in all phases – pre-primary, compulsory and upper-secondary – across all regions and communities?
2.3.5 Do monitoring <i>mechanisms</i> ensure that inequalities in access to educational resources at regional or organisational levels are addressed ?
2.3.6 Are there clear <i>mechanisms</i> to involve learners in the process of evaluating the quality of services ?

2.3.7 Are there clear <i>mechanisms</i> to involve families in the process of evaluating the quality of services ?
2.3.8 Are there transparent accountability frameworks at local level , including provision for appeals and arbitration?
2.3.9 Are <i>strategies</i> in place to regularly review accountability and quality assurance mechanisms to ensure they are fit for purpose?
2.3.10 Is there clear <i>guidance</i> for schools to develop the inclusiveness of the physical and social environment?
2.3.11 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to support schools to have ownership of review and improvement processes ?
2.3.12 Is there clear <i>guidance</i> for schools on the use of a range of different success measures that contribute to school self-review and evaluation processes?
2.3.13 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to share and analyse data to inform improvement processes at national, local and school levels?
2.3.14 Is clear <i>data</i> available on whether learners' rights to age-appropriate inclusive education are being implemented?
2.3.15 Are there clear <i>mechanisms</i> to identify schools with lower educational outcomes ?
2.3.16 Are there <i>strategies</i> to develop monitoring systems that use a wide range of academic and social achievements/outcomes ?

2.4 Initial and continuing professional development opportunities

This section examines whether the framework for and availability of initial teacher education (ITE) and continuing professional development (CPD) opportunities effectively meet the needs and requirements of the professionals and organisations working within the system for inclusive education.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include descriptions of systems for ITE and CPD, such as:

- regulations;
- national standards and competence criteria;
- support for newly-qualified teachers;
- resourcing and financing;
- evaluation frameworks and mechanisms;
- description of professional training and development opportunities for specialist/support staff.

Table 6. Mapping questions for initial and continuing professional development opportunities

2.4.1 Is there a formal <i>strategy</i> for promoting dialogue between ministries, regional/local authorities/municipalities and training providers to agree the requirements of all ITE and CPD opportunities?
2.4.2 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that all training opportunities are clearly aligned with national- and local-level policy goals for and understandings of inclusive education?
2.4.3 Is there a flexible funding mechanism for different forms of ITE and CPD that works to address local capacity-building issues?
2.4.4 Are there <i>requirements</i> for minimum levels of service provision in line with national and local policy for inclusive education to guide the work of all training providers?
2.4.5 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure the availability of high-quality and appropriately trained teacher educators ?
2.4.6 Is there a <i>strategy</i> to ensure a flexible continuum of diverse training opportunities for inclusive education across all ITE and CPD opportunities?
2.4.7 Are there clear <i>strategies</i> for developing school leadership competences for inclusive education in all relevant professional development opportunities?
2.4.8 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to support schools to develop strategic plans for staff training in inclusive education?

2.4.9 Is there a *strategy* to ensure **specialised training pathways for specialists** who support school communities to implement inclusive education?

2.4.10 Are there clear *strategies* to support **effective collaboration and joint work** between schools and higher education providers/universities?

2.4.11 Are there *strategies* to ensure that **local-level CPD opportunities are aligned with school development plans** to improve inclusive practice?

2.4.12 Is there a clear medium- and long-term **review strategy for ITE and CPD training possibilities** to ensure that they continue to meet system requirements?

2.5 Learning and teaching environments

This sub-section examines whether the learning process is guided by flexible curricula that ensure relevance to all learners, moving beyond academic content to include wider skills in preparation for life, work and personal development.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include:

- curricula framework guidelines;
- school admission procedures;
- Ombudsman's reports, etc.

Table 7. Mapping questions for learning and teaching environments

2.5.1 Is the curriculum and assessment <i>framework</i> underpinned by high expectations for all learners' achievements?
2.5.2 Does the curriculum and assessment <i>framework</i> support the effective use of teaching approaches that engage all learners and enable their active participation in learning?
2.5.3 Is the curriculum and assessment <i>framework</i> at all system levels periodically reviewed for relevance, accessibility and usability?
2.5.4 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that the system of formal school accreditation is meaningful for and open and fully accessible to all learners?
2.5.5 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to ensure that learners' voices are listened to in decision-making that affects them?
2.5.6 Are <i>strategies</i> in place to support all school leaders to adopt an inclusive approach , create a welcoming ethos and value diversity among staff as well as learners?
2.5.7 Is there a mechanism to ensure that schools are supported to develop school strategic plans for teaching and learning , centred upon high expectations for all learners?
2.5.8 Is there a mechanism to ensure that schools are supported to develop effective assessment for learning practice ?
2.5.9 Is there a mechanism to ensure that schools are supported to use school-level assessment, monitoring and evaluation data to guide their work?
2.5.10 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to support schools to actively engage with research that supports innovative teaching approaches?

2.6 Continua of support

This sub-section examines whether there is a support framework that enables all school-level stakeholders to take individual and collective responsibility for all learners, believing that everyone can become a better learner and achieve their learning goals.

The possible documents to be analysed in this sub-section include:

- descriptions of inclusive education and additional support services, including:
 - types of provision and support;
 - roles and responsibilities of key service providers (health services, psychologists, non-government organisations, etc.);
 - contracts and working agreements with service providers;
- descriptions of the role of any ‘diagnostic’ centres:
 - purpose and working methods;
 - role as a ‘gate-keeper’ of resources;
- descriptions of any regional resource centres:
 - roles;
 - working procedures;
 - numbers of schools, teachers and learners supported;
 - evaluation of practice;
- descriptions of special schools and units:
 - roles;
 - working procedures;
 - numbers of mainstream schools, teachers and learners supported;
 - evaluation of practice;
- Ombudsman’s reports.

Table 8. Mapping questions for continua of support

2.6.1 Are there flexible resource allocation mechanisms that increase the system’s capacity to be inclusive at all system levels?
2.6.2 Are <i>mechanisms</i> in place to identify learners’ support needs as early as possible ?
2.6.3 Are <i>mechanisms</i> in place to systematically monitor learners who are at risk of exclusion from learning opportunities?
2.6.4 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to support early identification and necessary advance planning for learners with more complex needs ?

2.6.5 Are there clear <i>strategies</i> to reduce the use of formal needs identification procedures that involve the labelling of learners as the main means to access support?
2.6.6 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to ensure that current systems for needs identification and support allocation are geared towards early intervention and prevention , rather than compensatory support?
2.6.7 Are there <i>mechanisms</i> to ensure that the work of all specialist support staff involved in formally assessing the needs of learners who require additional support effectively informs and supports teaching and learning?
2.6.8 Is there a coherent <i>framework</i> of educational support that is considered fit for purpose in meeting all learners' needs?
2.6.9 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that the educational support system works towards the goal of every learner having meaningful learning opportunities?
2.6.10 Are there <i>requirements</i> for the monitoring and review of specialist provision and support to ensure that it is effective, appropriate, sustainable and meets learners' identified needs?
2.6.11 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that the work of support services and inter-disciplinary teams is transparent, cost-effective and guided by service-level agreements that are monitored and reviewed on a regular basis?
2.6.12 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure the support system builds the capacity of school teams to move away from individual, compensatory resource provision towards pro-active and early intervention when barriers to learning become evident?
2.6.13 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that the support system provides school teams with opportunities for collaboration with peers and other professionals ?
2.6.14 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that the support system promotes learners' involvement in decision-making about their learning and school experiences?
2.6.15 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that the support system meets learners' individual needs through the provision of specialist support to respond to specific challenges faced by school teams ?
2.6.16 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to ensure that the support system meets learners' individual needs through the provision of specialist support to respond to specific challenges faced by families ?
2.6.17 Is there a <i>mechanism</i> to review the role of current specialist provision – separate schools and classes/units – across all system levels, in order to transform and re-focus the role of specialist support and expertise towards supporting mainstream school teams ?

2.6.18 Are *mechanisms* in place to ensure the availability of **co-ordinated cross-sectoral provision to meet the special educational needs of pre-primary children** and their families?

2.6.19 Are *mechanisms* in place to ensure the availability of **meaningful vocational education and training options for learners who require additional support** that support their transition from education to employment?

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